

Personalized LSTM-based alarm systems for hypoglycemia prevention in an intraperitoneal artificial pancreas

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Abstract—Prevention of hypoglycemia is a key aspect for efficient management of Type I diabetes. Alarm systems (ASs) are very useful to alert the patient in advance in case of hypoglycemia, allowing early intervention to avoid or mitigate the potential critical situation. Model-based ASs use patient models to predict the future glucose concentration and trigger alarms. In recent years neural networks, in particular Personalized Long Short-Term Memory Networks (PLSTMs) have shown very promising performances in glucose prediction. In this work, PLSTM-based AS for the prevention of hypoglycemia for an Artificial Pancreas is proposed. Preliminary results on a subgroup of 71 patients show that this system is able to predict almost all the potentially critical events (median TPR = 100%) with a precision of 57%. These promising techniques are under study to include also the remaining 29 problematic patients.

I. INTRODUCTION

Type 1 Diabetes (T1D) is a metabolic disease characterized by high Blood Glucose (BG) levels ($BG > 180$ mg/dl) due to a malfunction of the β -pancreatic cells responsible for insulin secretion. If not treated, this condition can cause serious short- and long-term complications, increasing the probability of cardiovascular diseases, neuropathies, nephropathies, and ocular problems [1]. It has been estimated that in 2019 the number of people with diabetes was 463 million (9.3% of the adult population between 20 and 79 years). This value is expected to rise to about 578 million in 2030, up to 700 million in 2045 (prevalence of 10.9%) [2]. Treatment of T1D involves exogenous insulin administration, which must be accurately defined to avoid both hyperglycemia ($BG > 180$ mg/dl) and hypoglycemia ($BG < 70$ mg/dl) phenomena. Various technologies have been introduced in recent years to aid diabetic patients in this challenging task, with the aim of improving glucose control and decreasing the workload of the subject [3], [4]. Of particular importance is the Artificial Pancreas (AP) [5], a closed-loop system which automatically calculates the optimal amount of insulin to be administered based on glucose data and additional information provided by the patient. The current AP systems use the subcutaneous (SC) glucose sensor and SC insulin pump, which involve not negligible delays on both sensing and actuation, particularly critical in the postprandial period. In order to overcome this problem, a so-called Hybrid Closed-Loop (HCL) approach is commonly used, requiring

the announcement of the carbohydrate content consumed by the patient to trigger a feed-forward action and promptly compensate the meal effect.

The intraperitoneal (IP) route for insulin delivery proved to be a promising alternative to the conventional SC one [6] overcoming the actuation delay and allowing the Fully-Automated (FA) closed-loop where no meal announcement is required. The EU funded in the last years different projects to design an implantable FA intraperitoneal AP; an example is an IP AP equipped with a new time-varying PID controller (PID_{IP}) with IP insulin delivery and IP glucose sensing which obtained promising results in silico [7].

An essential point in the diabetes management is to ensure the safety of the patient, avoiding both hyper and hypoglycemia phenomena: the AP is typically equipped with Alarm Systems (ASs) that alerts the subject in case of these critical situations. In the design of the AS, two main approaches can be considered: threshold detection or prediction-based systems. In the first, the alarm is raised if the glucose exceeds a certain threshold, while in the second it is possible to intervene in advance thanks to a prediction based on the patient model. In the latter, a key role is played by the model used for prediction. In recent years, thanks to the increasing availability of in vivo and in vitro data, machine learning techniques (multilayer perceptron, reinforcement learning techniques, and deep learning models [8], [9]) have proved very powerful in glucose prediction for the SC case. Among these, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) are particularly suitable as they specialize in data flow analysis. In particular, the Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network [10], [11] have been largely studied [12], [13], [14], [15], [16]: in particular in [12], [13], the LSTMs showed satisfactory glucose prediction having in input past glucose values, current meals and insulin (RMSE = 7.67 mg/dl). On the contrary, studies focused on the IP prediction problem are not available in literature. Only in [17], an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) has been trained to predict simulated glucose data in rats. In this work a personalized LSTM-based alarm systems for hypoglycemia prevention has been developed for the first time for the IP route.

The IP environment brings several limitations compared to traditional SC: first, the data collection is more complex and, second, the number of patients using this technology is low, limiting the availability of large IP datasets. Moreover, the generality of the represented conditions is limited, considering the large inter-individual variability existing between patients. This aspect calls for Personalized LSTM (PLSTM) and AS, as already studied in SC case [13].

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Fig. 1. Scheme of a single LSTM-cell

The purpose of this work is to exploit PLSTM for glucose prediction also in the IP case (IP-PLSTM) and to design a PLSTM-based AS (IP-PLSTM-AS) to deal with disturbances, such as physical exercise or unexpected changes in the insulin sensitivity. In this work, the innovative approach is the use of the LSTMs to model only the well-controlled conditions in which the datasets can be collected and then activate the alarm system when the quality of the prediction degrades over a certain threshold. In fact, it highlights unexpected behaviour of the glucose trend due to disturbances and/or alteration of the insulin sensitivity the AS has to detect. In [18] preliminary results over a population of 10 subjects of the UVA/Padova simulator [7] were presented; in this paper those techniques have been extended and personalized for the entire population of 100 T1D patients, leading to two different configurations for two classes of patients.

The remaining part of the paper is organized in 4 main sections: Section II introduce the PLSTMs used for glucose prediction and the design procedure of the IP-PLSTM-AS based on them; Section III introduce the datasets characteristics and the performance metrics used to evaluate the results; Section IV reports the results and discusses strengths and weaknesses of the method; finally, the conclusions are drawn in Section V.

II. METHODS

A. Personalized LSTM for IP route

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks [10] are particular RNNs that, thanks to their unitary structure, the memory cells, improve the performance of traditional RNNs solving the vanishing gradient problem [19]: in the memory cells the flow of information is regulated by an internal recurrence additional to the external self-loop of the RNNs, and by a gating system. In this way, the gradient can flow during time, even for long periods, and its derivatives do not explode nor vanish. A single memory cell (Figure 1) can be described by the following equations:

$$c_k = f(u_k, h_{k-1}) \times c_{k-1} + i(u_k, h_{k-1}) \times \tilde{c}(u_k, h_{k-1})$$

$$h_k = o(u_k, h_{k-1}) \times \tanh(c_k)$$

where $c_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_c}$ is the internal cell state at time k , $h_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_c}$ the hidden state, with n_c the dimension of the cell state that is equal to the number of LSTM neurons. $u_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ is the input, with n_u the number of features. \times is the Hadamard product and \tanh is the hyperbolic tangent, used as activation function. The four gates f, i, \tilde{c} and o compose the internal loop of the cell and add or remove information to modify the value of the cell state:

- f , the forget gate, determines which information is removed from the cell state c_k ;
- i , the input gate, decides which value of the cell state c_k is updated;
- \tilde{c} , the input activation gate, creates a new candidate value of the cell state c_k
- o , the output gate, determines which information contained in the cell state c_k goes in output.

Defining as $W_f, W_i, W_o, W_c \in \mathbb{R}^{n_c \times n_u}$ the input weight matrices, as $U_f, U_i, U_o, U_c \in \mathbb{R}^{n_c \times n_c}$ the previous output weight matrices and as $b_f, b_i, b_o, b_c \in \mathbb{R}^{n_c \times 1}$ the biases, with σ the sigmoid function, the four gates are described by the following equations:

$$f(u_k, h_{k-1}) = \sigma(W_f u_k + U_f h_{k-1} + b_f)$$

$$i(u_k, h_{k-1}) = \sigma(W_i u_k + U_i h_{k-1} + b_i)$$

$$\tilde{c}(u_k, h_{k-1}) = \tanh(W_c u_k + U_c h_{k-1} + b_c)$$

$$o(u_k, h_{k-1}) = \sigma(W_o u_k + U_o h_{k-1} + b_o)$$

The LSTM network can be composed by one or more layers, and each layer by a certain number of neurons n_c . The output of the second last layer is passed to the last one, called fully connected layer to obtain the final output of the network y_k :

$$y_k = W_y h_k + b_y$$

where $W_y \in \mathbb{R}^{n_p \times n_c}$ is the matrix of the output weight, with n_p the number of outputs of the network, and b_y the bias. All the matrices and the parameters are determined in the training phase of the network. Considering the huge inter-patient variability, the training phase will be performed independently for each subject selecting the specific optimal hyperparameters for the single individual and giving rise to a Personalized-LSTM (PLSTM).

In previous works [13], [12], PLSTMs developed for the 100 in silico patients of the UVA/Padova simulator [20] obtained promising results in the SC case. These PLSTMs, having in input past glucose values, current meals and current insulin quantities, were able to well predict future glucose concentrations taking into account inter-patients variability. Starting from these promising results, in this work the strategy has been adapted to the FA CL environment, where the meal announcement is not provided: selecting as input glucose and insulin information only, the problem of glucose prediction becomes even more challenging.

The PLSTM proposed in this work (IP-PLSTM) is characterized by a single layer and a fully connected layer, with two inputs ($n_u = 2$) and one output ($n_p = 1$). The inputs u_k are the past glucose values $G(k - PH)$ and the past injected insulin $I(k - PH)$ of PH minutes before, with $PH = 20$ [min] as a

compromise between the time horizon length and the quality of predictive performance [15]; the output y_k is the glucose value at the current time, $G(k)$. The number of neurons n_c is used for the personalization of the network.

PLSTMs are trained using Adaptive Moment Estimation (Adam) optimizer to perform the back propagation algorithm, with Mean Squared Error (MSE) as the loss function L :

$$L = MSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$$

with y and \hat{y} a signal of interest and its prediction, and N the total number of samples of y . This minimization is an iterative process, where at each iteration j , called epoch, the gradient of L with respect to the weights w is calculated, to update the weights in the opposite direction with respect to the gradient:

$$w(j+1) = w(j) - \alpha \frac{d}{dw} L(w(j))$$

where α is the learning rate, that determines the step size at each iteration. In this work α and the number of epochs n_e are optimized for each patient; they vary in the intervals [0.001 0.01] with step = 0.01 and [32 512] with step = 32, respectively. The training of the PLSTMs is implemented with TensorFlow and Keras API, and the hyperparameters are optimized using KerasTuner. The training has been carried out using a computer equipped with graphics processing unit (GPU) NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1050, an Intel i7-7700HQ CPU with 2.80 GHz and 32.0 GB memory. The program is written in Python 3.6, using CUDA 9.0.

B. Personalized LSTM-based Alarm System

An alarm system is a useful tool for the glucose controller to ensure patient safety. The performances of the model-based AS strictly depend on the quality of the prediction. The proposed PLSTM network is trained to reliably predict the glucose of the well-controlled patient, whose glucose trend remains mostly in the safe range. As a result, an AS activated by the degradation of the prediction performance is proposed to trigger recovery actions in case of unexpected potentially critical situations. An example is reported in Figure 2 where the PLSTM prediction is accurate in the well-controlled periods, while during hypoglycemia event it is not able to follow the glucose trend and the degradation of the prediction performances should raise an alarm.

It is important to note that the conditions to activate the alarms represent a key point to obtain good performance. Defining as $G(k)$ the glucose measured by the sensor at time k , $\hat{G}(k)$ the predicted glucose signal at time k performed with $PH=20$ [min] and as $\Delta G_{t^*, \bar{t}}$ the difference between the glucose values at t^* and \bar{t} , ($\Delta G_{t^*, \bar{t}}(k) = G_{t^*}(k) - G_{\bar{t}}(k)$), the proposed AS is activated in three cases:

- a) if three conditions are verified contemporary:
 - $\Delta G(k) = \hat{G}(k) - G(k) > th_{\Delta a}$ with $\hat{G} < th_{a1}$, $G < th_{a2}$: the deviations of the prediction from the measured glucose are greater than a certain threshold $th_{\Delta a}$ in condition of potential hypoglycemia (both

Fig. 2. AS example: during hypoglycemia events the PLSTM performances degrade and an alarm is raised.

the samples below certain glucose thresholds, th_{a1} and th_{a2}).

- $\Delta \hat{G}_{t^*+20, t^*+10}(k) > th_{a3}$ and $\Delta \hat{G}_{t^*+20, t^*}(k) > th_{a3}$, or $\Delta G_{t^*, t^*-5}(k) > th_{a3}$: the measured glucose or the prediction have significantly decreasing trends.
 - $\Delta \hat{G}_{t^*-15, t^*-20}(k) < th_{a4}$ and $\Delta \hat{G}_{t^*-20, t^*-25}(k) < th_{a4}$: the predicted signal should not grow too fast, in order to limit alarms due to delayed predictions.
- b) if \hat{G} deviates from G more than a high threshold and G is below a restrictive threshold:
 - $\Delta G(k) = \hat{G}(k) - G(k) > th_{\Delta b}$ with $G < th_{b1}$.
 - c) if $\hat{G}_{t^*+20}(k)$ is below 80 mg/dl, and \hat{G} is decreasing.

The parameters $th_{\Delta a}$, th_{a1} , th_{a2} , th_{a3} , th_{a4} , $th_{\Delta b}$, th_{b1} are personalized in order to take into account inter-patient variability.

C. Personalized AS configurations based on PLSTM performance

ASs are typically based on population thresholds; for example, in [13] an alarm is generated if the predicted glucose crosses the threshold of 70 mg/dl. Considering the high inter-patient variability, the considered problems calls for personalized threshold. Since in this work the AS activation depends on the characteristics of the predicted glucose with respect to the measured one, and considering the high inter-patient variability, also the AS thresholds have to be patient-tailored. In order to avoid trial and error approaches to define 100 threshold configurations, these configurations have been defined as function of patient specific characteristics: the prediction performances of each individual PLSTM, or the measured glucose G of each patient, reducing the parameters to be identified.

Consider the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) which quantifies the variance of the prediction error, computed as $RMSE(y, \hat{y}) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}$, with y and \hat{y} a signal of interest and its prediction, respectively, and N the total number of samples of y ; define the mean value of a signal y as \bar{y} and its standard deviation as $SD(y)$; considering the function $percentile(X, p)$ which return the percentile value of input data X for the percentages p in $[0, 100]$, the thresholds

can be defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
th_{\Delta a}(RMSE) &= \alpha_{\Delta a} * RMSE(G, \hat{G}) \\
th_{a1}(\hat{G}) &= \tilde{G} + \alpha_{a1} * SD(\hat{G}) \\
th_{a2}(G) &= \tilde{G} - \alpha_{a2} * SD(G) \\
th_{a3}(\Delta \hat{G}_{t^*, \bar{t}}) &= percentile(\Delta G_{t^*, \bar{t}}, \alpha_{a3}) \\
th_{a4}(\Delta G_{t^*, \bar{t}}) &= percentile(\Delta G_{t^*, \bar{t}}, \alpha_{a4}) \\
th_{\Delta b}(RMSE) &= \alpha_{\Delta b} * RMSE(G, \hat{G}) \\
th_{b1}(G) &= \tilde{G} - \alpha_{b1} * SD(G)
\end{aligned}$$

where $\alpha_{\Delta a}$, α_{a1} , α_{a2} , α_{a3} , α_{a4} , $\alpha_{\Delta b}$, α_{b1} are the parameters to be defined. In this work, a part of these parameters have been assumed constant for the entire population, in particular $\alpha_{\Delta a} = 1.5$, $\alpha_{a3} = 95$, $\alpha_{\Delta b} = 6$, $\alpha_{b1} = 1$. For the others, two main configurations are considered: Configuration A, $\alpha_{a1} = 0.5$, $\alpha_{a2} = 0.2$, $\alpha_{a4} = 90$, and Configuration B where $\alpha_{a1} = 1.5$, $\alpha_{a2} = 0.5$, $\alpha_{a4} = 100$, to maximize the number of events correctly detected by the alarm system.

III. DATASETS

A. Datasets simulation

In this work four different datasets have been generated to train the PLSTM and to evaluate the performance of both PLSTM and AS: a training dataset (tr-dt), used to train the PLSTMs; a validation dataset (v-dt) for the hyperparameters tuning; a testing dataset (ts-dt), used to assess the network performance and a second testing dataset (ts*-dt) to test the AS performance. The datasets are simulated using the IP-modified FDA UVA/Padova Simulator [21], a new version of simulator that takes into account the IP dynamics. The UVA/Padova Simulator has been accepted by the Food and Drug Administration as a substitute to animal trials in the preclinical testing of closed-loop control strategies for diabetes management. It is equipped with an in silico population of 100 adult subjects spanning the variability observed in the real T1D population [20], [22].

The tr-dt and ts-dt last 10 days and the v-dt 4 days, all with well regulated glucose traces, while the ts*-dt is ts-dt with patient's insulin sensitivity altered to simulate unexpected conditions, e.g. physical activity, and to bring the subject into hypoglycemia, in order to check the AS detection features. In particular, the insulin sensitivity parameters (k_{p3} , V_{mx} of the Dalla Man model [23]) is changed for 1 hour, from 18:00 to 19:00, in days 1,2,5,7 and 9. This alteration makes the patient more responsive to insulin action and causes hypoglycemia events which are necessary to evaluate AS performances in predicting critical situations. The meal scenario has been generated using a probabilistic model [24] that describes the average eating habits of Italian T1D subjects identified on real patients, which distribution is described in Table I:

B. Performance Index

In order to evaluate both PLSTM and AS performances, different metrics have to be defined. In order to properly set the AS, the PLSTM has to show good predictive performance for tr-dt and v-dt, where the glucose traces are

TABLE I
AVERAGE MEAL DISTRIBUTION OF ITALIAN T1D SUBJECTS

	Meals	CHO	Time
tr-dt	Breakfast	45.3g (\pm 3.6g)	08:25 (\pm 60 min)
	Lunch	60.3g (\pm 3.2g)	13:25 (\pm 63 min)
	Dinner	74g [26g, 77g]	20:43(\pm 56 min)
	Snacks	20g (\pm 5g)	
v-dt	Breakfast	46g [42.5g, 47.2g]	08:54 (\pm 65 min)
	Lunch	59.2g (\pm 3.1g)	13:09 (\pm 74 min)
	Dinner	76g [67g, 78g]	20:19 (\pm 76 min)
	Snacks	20g (\pm 5g)	
ts-dt	Breakfast	44g [43g, 47.2g]	08:21 (\pm 58 min)
	Lunch	59g (\pm 2.2g)	13:07 [13:00, 14:00]
	Dinner	74.5g [67g, 79g]	20:19 (\pm 90 min)
	Snacks	20g (\pm 5g)	

well-controlled. The following performance metrics are then considered:

- the index of fitting (FIT), a normalized index that indicates how much the prediction matches the real data. Perfect prediction corresponds to FIT = 100%:

$$FIT = 100 \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \|\hat{y}_i - y_i\|}{\sum_{i=1}^N \|y_i - \bar{y}_i\|} \right)$$

- the RMSE (see Section II-C)

where y and \hat{y} are the measured signal and its prediction, respectively; \bar{y} the mean of y and $\|\cdot\|$ the norm of the signal; N corresponds of the total number of samples of y .

In order to evaluate the AS performance, the following events are defined:

- True Positive (TP) if an alarm is raised at least 10 minutes before the real event and no more than 1 hour before;
- False Positive (FP) if an alarm is raised when there is no a real event; it is important to notice that if an alarm is raised too late, it is not considered a FP even if it is not counted as a TP. In fact, it is a correct detection (TP) that is not raised enough in advance to take an action to avoid hypoglycemia. In this prospect, those events are not taken into account in the results;
- False Negative (FN) if in correspondence of a hypoglycemia event no alarm is raised.

Since the dataset is imbalanced (few positive events), in accordance with [25] the informative metrics are:

- True Positive Rate (TPR), which measures how many events are correctly detected by the alarm system on the total number of events:

$$TPR = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

- Precision (Pr), which measures how many alarms are correctly raised on the total number of the activated alarms:

$$Pr = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

These metrics have been evaluated on the entire population of 100 in silico patients in terms of mean (\pm SD) or median [25th, 75th] percentiles if the results are normally or not normally distributed, respectively. The gaussianity of the data distributions is assessed by the Lilliefors test.

IV. RESULTS

A. PLSTM results

The prediction results of the PLSTM on the entire in silico IP population of 100 T1D subjects are reported in Table II.

TABLE II
PREDICTION PERFORMANCES

	tr-dt	v-dt	ts-dt
FIT [%]	73.7 [67.2, 78.1]	71.3 (\pm 8.3)	68.0 (\pm 9.7)
RMSE [mg/dl]	4.6 (\pm 1.5)	5.6 [4.2, 7.4]	5.4 [4.4, 6.8]

Overall, the PLSTMs demonstrate good predictive performances both in the tr-dt and in the v-dt, as expected. The PLSTMs show good results also on unseen dataset (ts-dt) with a FIT of 68%. The design of the AS proposed in this work is then carried out exploiting these models. The predicted performance on the ts*-dt (FIT=60.2, RMSE=7.5) degrades since some dynamics have not been learnt by the neural network. In fact, the performances are decreases by the inability of the network to predict the hypoglycemia events; however, the overall performances remain acceptable. It is worthy to note that the glucose prediction without the meal information is a particularly challenging task. As reported in [26], similar performances have been obtained by Aliberti [27] (RMSE=7.18) exploiting a huge population of 451 in vivo subjects treated via SC route. The limited amount and dimension of the datasets for a single subject increase the complexity of the prediction task, making these preliminary results satisfactory.

B. AS results

For the alarm system two main configurations are considered, Configuration A and Configuration B (defined in Section II-C) with different parameter settings. Since the subjects are very different from each other, it is not possible to determine which of the two alternatives is uniquely better on the whole population. The best solution is to identified for each patient the best configuration via a trial and error procedure. Overall, promising performance have been obtained ($TPR > 50\%$) for 71 patients over the 100 of the total population (Table III). Configuration A has better performances for 20 patients, Configuration B is better for 24 subject and for the remaining 27 subjects the results of the two settings are comparable. For the subset of 71 patients, the

TABLE III
PERFORMANCES OF THE AS ON 71 IN SILICO SUBJECTS

TPR [%]	Pr [%]
100 [75 100]	57 [33.3 100]

system can reliably detect all critical events ($TPR = 100\%$), ensuring the safety of subjects. This is particularly relevant in an IP system where the patient cannot interact directly with the glucose controller and the insulin pump, and where there is no meal announcement. The proposed AS is therefore highly reliable. However, it is important to observe that alarms are raised correctly in 57% of cases ($Pr = 57\%$), which is acceptable but not optimal. A possible extension of this work consists in a deeper study of the patients with many false positives, in order to identify their causes and try to solve the problem. In addition, for a limited number of 29 patients the two proposed configurations does not give adequate performances with a $TPR < 50\%$. The cause can be double: an inadequate configuration of the AS or a not appropriate glucose prediction (e.g. characterized by not negligible delays). Then, for this subgroup of subjects a possible approach could consist in the design of an automatic and individual calibration procedure of the AS parameters. On the other hand, PLSTM performances have to be evaluated in detail to identify eventually specific causes of the alarm detection failure of hypoglycemia events.

Fig. 3. AS example: the alarm is raised too close to the hypoglycemia event due to some delays in the PLSTM prediction.

An example of a problematic case is shown in Figure 3: the PLSTM predicts the glucose trend with good performances but the prediction is characterized by not negligible delays with respect to the real signal. This fact can lead the AS to a late detection of the hypoglycemia events. Overall, this subject presents 5 hypoglycemia events over 10 days of monitoring: two of them are detected in time, while three are correctly detected but not sufficiently in advance. In particular, the detection occurs 5 minutes, 5 minutes and 7 minutes before the hypoglycemia events not allowing promptly actions to avoid them. One possible future development to overcome this problem could be the inclusion in the loss function of a term which weights these delays.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper a new alarm system for the prevention of hypoglycemia in intraperitoneal artificial pancreas is presented. The model-based AS exploits the glucose prediction obtained via PLSTMs, patient-tailored neural networks customized for each specific subject of the considered population. PLSTMs are trained on well-controlled datasets, and therefore to predict the patient's well-controlled glucose trends in nominal

conditions. Taking in input past glucose and past insulin, the PLSTMs reliably predict the future glucose concentration with PH = 20 minutes, with a FIT index of 68% and an RMSE equal to 5.4 mg/dl on the 100 in silico subjects generated with the UVA/Padova Simulator. These performances allow the design of the AS, which alert the patient in case of unexpected glucose trends corresponding to potentially critical situations. To manage the high variability among patients, also the proposed IP-PLSTM-AS is individually customized depending both on glucose signal characteristics and on the predictive performance of the network. Promising performances have been obtained on a subset of 71 patients out of 100, with median values of TPR = 100% and Pr = 57%. The system therefore demonstrates high reliability as it is able to detect all events potentially dangerous for the patient. This aspect is fundamental especially in IP environment where there is the possibility to intervene directly on the controller with external actions e.g. through meal announcement. The precision of the AS is acceptable but sub-optimal. Possible future developments include the study of patients with many FP to understand the cause of these problems and correct them. Moreover, for a subgroup of 29 patients the proposed configurations are not reliable, with a TPR index < 50%. Possible approach to overcome these problems include ad hoc parameter configurations for AS or the design of specific training phase (e.g. considering the delays in the loss function) to improve the prediction performances. These actions are currently under study.

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